

ABRomics metadata

Progress of the β version release

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Metadata type

Biological sample	Mandatory							
	Sample type	Host species	Sample source (for human or animal)	Sample source (for environment)	Sample country	Sample ZIP code	Sample date	Original sample ID
	Optional							
	GPS latitude	GPS longitude	Sample collected by	Sample collector contact email	Travel country	Sample comment		

Strain	Mandatory		Optional	
	Microorganism scientific name	Strain ID (or name)	Microorganism subspecies	NCBI taxonomy ID

- **Minimal** metadata are *mandatory* for the:
 - biological sample
 - strain
 - sequencing
- **Detailed** metadata are *optional*
- **Controlled vocabularies** for standardized entry

Sequencing	Mandatory			
	Instrument model	R1 fastq filename	R2 fastq filename	Sequencing partner

Controlled metadata validation

Datawarehouse

Field name	Description/guidelines for ABRomics users	ABRomics status	Type	Accepted values / validation	Additional comments	Metadata type
Sample type	Indicate if the sample is collected on human, on animal, in an environment or another source (other, eg, food). "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list "Sample type" in the Fields_values tab.	mandatory	string	(human, animal, environment, other)	Metagenome and genome	

Field name	Description/guidelines for ABRomics users	ABRomics status	Type	Accepted values / validation	Additional comments	Metadata type
Host species	Species of the host. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate "Not collected information is missing).					
Sample source (for human or animal)	Site of isolation for samples collected on human or animal. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate "Not collected information is missing).					
Sample source (for environment)	Site of isolation for samples collected in an environment. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate "Not collected information is missing).					
Sample country	Name of the country in which the sample has been collected. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate either "Not collected" or "XX" (if information is missing).					
Sample ZIP code	ZIP code of the location where the sampling was performed. The latitude coordinates of the geographical location where the sampling was performed.					
GPS latitude	"Accepted values / validation" column: must be specified decimal degrees latitude in format "d.dddd", eg. 38.9 Latitude must be between -90.0000 and 90.0000 degree. The longitude coordinates of the geographical location where the sampling was performed.					
GPS longitude	"Accepted values / validation" column: must be specified decimal degrees longitude in format "d.dddd", eg. 77.11 Longitude must be between -180.0000 and 180.0 degrees.					
Sample date	The date of sampling. "Accepted values / validation" column: must be in this format: "DD/MM/YYYY".					
Original sample ID	ID of the sample emitted by the sampling laboratory. "Accepted values / validation" column: Original sample value must be unique in the whole document.					
Sample collected by	Name of the person or name of the institution that collected the sample.	optional	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
Sample collector contact email	Contact email address of the person/institution to contact.	optional	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
Travel country	Countries where the host travelled to in the last 3 months prior to the sampling (list multiple countries with comma-separated values). "Accepted values / validation" column: choose from the list "Country list (alpha-2 code)" in the Fields_values tab.	optional	string	free text: Country 2-letters code, see the list in Field_values tab. Country english full name is not accepted. If multiple countries, separate each by comma.	Metagenome and genome	
Sample comment	Any comments on the sample.	optional	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
Microorganism scientific name	Scientific name of the isolated microorganism. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values.	mandatory	string	[Escherichia coli, Shigella spp., Klebsiella pneumoniae, Klebsiella aerogenes, Enterobacter cloacae, Citrobacter freundii, Citrobacter koseri, Morganella morganii, Salmonella enterica, Staphylococcus aureus, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Acinetobacter baumannii, Enterococcus faecalis, Enterococcus faecium, Campylobacter jejuni, Campylobacter coli, Campylobacter fetus, Campylobacter lari, Campylobacter upsaliensis, Campylobacter ornithocola, Campylobacter armoricus, Alarcobacter butzleri, Arcobacter cryaerophilus, Helicobacter pylori, Helicobacter pullorum, Helicobacter cinaedi, Arcobacter caviae, Proteus mirabilis]	Genome	S T R A I N
Microorganism subspecies	Name of the sub-species of the isolated microorganism.	optional	string	free text	Genome	
Strain ID (or name)	Name of the isolated strain. "Accepted values / validation" column: Strain ID (or name) value must be unique in the whole document.	mandatory	string	free text	Genome	
NCBI taxonomy ID	NCBI taxonomy ID of the isolated microorganism. "Accepted values / validation" column: NCBI taxonomy ID value must be superior to 0.	optional	integer	number superior to 0	Genome	
Instrument model	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list.	mandatory	string	(HiSeq X Five, HiSeq X Ten, Illumina HiScanSQ, Illumina HiSeq 1000, Illumina HiSeq 1500, Illumina HiSeq 2000, Illumina HiSeq 2500, Illumina HiSeq 3000, Illumina HiSeq 4000, Illumina iSeq 100, Illumina MiSeq, Illumina MiSeqSeq, Illumina NovaSeq 6000, NovaSeq 500, NovaSeq 550, PacBio RS, PacBio RS II, Sequel, Ion Torrent PGM, Ion Torrent Proton, Ion Torrent S5, Ion Torrent S5 XL, MinION, GridION, PromethION, BGISEQ-500, DNBSSEQ-T7, DNBSSEQ-G400, DNBSSEQ-G50, DNBSSEQ-G400 FAST)	Metagenome and genome	S E Q U E N C I N G
R1 fastq filename	Name of the fastq forward file. "Accepted values / validation" column: free text BUT the file name must end by ".1.fastq.gz"	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
R2 fastq filename	Name of the fastq reverse file. "Accepted values / validation" column: free text BUT the file name must end by ".2.fastq.gz"	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
Sequencing partner	The name of the agency that did the sequencing.	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	

	Fields	Mandatory
Sample	14	8
Isolate	4	2
Sequencing	4	4

14 out of 22 fields are mandatory

formatted to follow the **ENA prokaryotic pathogen minimal sample checklist** (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000028>) for submission

Access to the complete excel file :

Lien Zenodo : <https://zenodo.org/record/8283174>